

Effect of heat waves in processing tomato yields

C. Campillo¹, A. Vergara¹, E. Márquez¹, E. Mendoza², J. Blanco², J. Cristobal³, M.V. Alarcón¹

¹Centre for Scientific and Technological Research of Extremadura (CICYTEX), Department of Horticulture, Finca La Orden, Regional Government of Extremadura, Highway A-V, Km 372, 06187 Guadajira, Badajoz, Spain.

(2) Greenfield Technologies S.L. Plaza de España, 6, 3º Pta.2 06002 Badajoz (Spain)

(3) Departament de Geografia. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Carrer de la Fortuna, Edifici B 08193 Bellaterra (Cerdanyola del Vallès) Spain.

Abstract

In the current climate change environment, heat waves are becoming more frequent and more intense because of maximum and minimum temperature increases. Heat waves are prolonged periods of high temperature and excessive heat with significant impacts on natural and human ecosystems. In processing tomatoes, a heat wave is considered an episode whenever temperatures exceed 35 °C for at least 3 consecutive days. The aims of the present work, included in the activities developed in the DIGISPAC and ETDROUGHT projects was to study the trends and effects of the heat waves in the main production area of Spain, the “Vegas Altas” and “Vegas Bajas” del Guadiana (Extremadura), through the analysis of semi-hourly data from 5 climate stations in the region (years 2018 to 2023) and the yield of approximately 1,000 field data points. Thus, it has been observed that over the last 20 years the number of days with maximum temperatures equal to or exceeding 35 °C has increased, causing negative effects on the yield of the plots studied. Based on these results, 5-day climate prediction models and satellite imagery appear to be potentially useful tools to identify areas susceptible to heat waves. The data obtained from the analysis of the critical moment coincided with the period of abnormally high maximum and minimum temperatures, which occurred in the years considered as heat wave. This period was identified as critical for the crop, coinciding with the flowering and fruit set phases. The data indicated that plots where the crop was in the critical period experienced a decrease in production. In contrast, crops outside this period did not show a significant decrease in production, which makes it essential to know when the crop is in the critical period to carry out historical studies on the effect of heat stress on the tomato crop and to develop mitigation strategies. Crop phenology, deduced through NDVI, can determine critical moments during thermal stress events. Therefore, future studies are needed to compare information from a larger number of plots, aiming to establish protocols and implement management techniques that mitigate heat damage in processing tomatoes.

Keywords: Vegas del Guadiana, climate change, high temperature, NDVI, yield, hot weather, warm up, *Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main problems when talking about heat waves is that there will not be a unique and precise definition for this term: what values do temperatures have to reach during a specific period to be considered as suffering from this phenomenon, how many days must it be maintained? And how large must the affected area be? (AEMET, 2019). For this reason, each author and meteorological agency has its concept of heat wave, which it uses in its determinations. A heat wave is an episode of at least three consecutive days in which at least 10 % of the stations considered record maximums above the 95 % percentile of their daily maximum temperature series for the months of July and August for the period 1971 - 2000" (AEMET, 2019). This definition adds the parameter of location to agree on a threshold temperature. In the Vegas del Gadiana area (Extremadura), the 95 % percentile is at 39 °C.

Heat waves are prolonged periods of high temperature and excess heat, significantly impacting natural and human ecosystems (Perkins, 2015). These exceptional events have been increasing in frequency, duration, and intensity in recent years (Lorenzo et al., 2021). Critical weather events can have very detrimental impacts on crop yields (Lesk et al., 2016), affecting food supply and commodity prices (Heinicke et al., 2022). Heat damage is uneven and numerous in tomato plants, especially in processing varieties, which are planted entirely in the open (WPTC, 2023). Sato et al. (2000) concluded that the most sensitive period to a moderate increase in temperature occurs between 8 and 13 days before anthesis, these two weeks being critical for development, with stress affecting pollen development, fruit growth, respiration, cell wall structure and, ultimately, production (Alsamir et al., 2021). Among all these problems, several studies conclude that the main damage plants suffer after increasing temperatures will occur in pollen grains and, ultimately, androecium (Alsamir et al., 2021). Heat stress not only induces bud, flower and fruit drop (Levy et al., 1978) but also causes deformations in the anthers by repressing the activity of the gene responsible for their growth and development (Müller et al., 2016); it reduces fertilisation by hindering the germination of the pollen tube in the style (Iwahori, 1966), and disrupts the process of microsporogenesis. On the latter point, several negative effects have reported on both the viability (Xu et al., 2017; Miller et al., 2021) and quantity (Paupière et al., 2017) of pollen produced. The optimal temperature range is essential for successful tomato cultivation. The ideal temperature range for tomatoes is between 18-25 °C, with the most significant development occurring between 21-24 °C. However, there are variations based on the plant's growth stage. During flowering, ideal daytime temperatures are 23-26 °C and 13-16 °C at night. Temperatures below 12 °C may stop growth, while temperatures above 35 °C may interrupt flowering and fruit set (Guzmán et al., 2017). It's important to consider relative humidity as well. Tomato plants are sensitive to humidity levels; the optimal range is 65-75 % (Baudoin, 2017). High temperatures combined with high humidity can increase disease proliferation, reduced stomatal closure, and growth cessation.

This work aims to evaluate heat waves dynamics in the central processing tomato growing areas of Extremadura, "Vegas Bajas" and "Vegas Altas" del Gadiana; to identify the years in which heat waves occurred and to evaluate the effect of temperature and the phenological moment of the crop on production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in 2023, as part of the DIGISPAC and ET4DROUGHT projects. For this work, the temperatures obtained at different agro-meteorological stations (orange symbols) distributed in the two main processing tomato growing areas: "Vegas Bajas del Guadina" (VB, green) and "Vegas Altas del Gadiana" (VA, purple), were evaluated (Figure 1). Air temperature values recorded every 30 minutes were analyzed for the last six years

(2018-2023). Historical data from stations over the last 20 years including daily maximum air temperature data were also analyzed.

Figure 1. Agro-meteorological stations located in the main production areas for processing tomatoes in Extremadura. The plots for processing tomatoes in 2023 are shown in red.

Production data were obtained from surveys carried out on different commercial plots between 2017 and 2022. About 1000 yield data were evaluated, 823 plots in VB and 103 plots in VA. Data were obtained directly from farmers participating in the young farmer support program, Greenfield, CONESA and Cooperativas Agroalimentarias de Extremadura.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows, in red, the days of each month and year when temperatures above 35 °C were recorded at the studied weather stations, with heat waves mainly occurring in VB and VA during July and August. The analysis of the last six years shows that the years with the highest number of days with temperatures above 35 °C in most of the studied stations were 2020, 2022 and 2023, considered years in which heat waves could have impacted on average production. In addition, the first weeks of July (main flowering period of the average plantings made during the second half of April and the first half of May) of the years 2020 and 2022 had the highest number of days with temperatures above 35 °C. On most of the dates studied, June is a month without days with temperatures above 35 °C and without heat waves, considering three consecutive days with temperatures above 35 °C (Figure 2). This is interesting from the point of view of evaluating the possibilities of establishing early transplants in late March and early April to ensure flowering in June.

Figure 2. Days with temperature over 35 °C from agrometeorological weather station in different years during main production month in processing tomato in VA and VB.

In addition, an analysis of how the climate has changed over the last 20 years in the stations studied was carried out to assess whether there has been an increased incidence of heat waves in recent years. Analysing the temperature data of the last 20 years recorded at two reference stations in VA and VB, a slight increase in the number of heat waves is observed, although this increase is more pronounced in VB (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Evaluation of the number of the heat waves per year in last 20 years in VB (left) and VA (right).

The average number of heat waves per year is usually 6 in VB and 5 in VA, although the year with the highest number of heat waves was 2016, with 10 and 9 heat waves in VB and VA, respectively, compared to 8 observed in 2004, 2006, 2015, and 2023. The data analysed did not detect a clear significant pattern of increasing heat waves in recent years, detecting more of a year-specific factor, with heat waves being cyclical and not consecutive.

However, when analysing the number of days when the crop was in a heat wave situation (Figure 4) and above 35 °C (Figure 5), the number of days has increased significantly over the last 20 years, with the number of days doubling in both areas, although more significantly in VA.

Figure 4. Evaluation of the number of the days in heat waves in last 20 years in VB (left) and VA (right).

In the last ten years, on average of approximately 50 days per year have been recorded with temperatures exceeding 35 °C. This can affect crop production, as reduced flowering, fruit damage and changes in crop cycles (accumulated degree days) can affect the final quality of the crop.

Figure 5. Evaluation of the number of days over 35 °C in last 20 years in VB (left) and VA (right).

Recent years have shown a trend of increasing average maximum temperature in July, exceeding 35 °C in both areas (Figure 6). This trend could significantly impact on the transplanting process, which coincides with the peak flowering and fruit set period. The increasing warmth pushes the growing conditions beyond the optimal range of development, which could pose a potential threat to the crop. However, it's important to note that is not a consistent trend. In 2020, 2022 and 202, July temperatures above 35 °C were recorded, while in 2021 they were below this mark, indicating a certain level of variability.

Figure 6. Evaluation of mean of maximum temperature in July in last 20 years in VB (left) and VA (right). Red zone data over 35 °C and green zone above.

The temperature has increased, but its impact on crop conditions varies depending on the specific year. To evaluate the effects of years characterized by frequent heat waves, we have chosen VB and VA producers from a range of reference years (2017-2022).

The yield of 823 plots in VB and 103 plots in VA was evaluated over several years (Figure 7). In VB, production is significantly variable between years, maintaining an average of 80-90 t ha⁻¹ commercial production (Figure 7a). 2017 and 2020 are the years with the lowest variability. The year 2020 was the year with the lowest production values, with plots with production data below 50 t ha⁻¹, coinciding with a year in which heat waves were recorded. In the case of 2019 and 2021, low yields were also recorded, although there were also plots with high yields. In the case of the plots analysed in VA, 2021 and 2022 were the most productive years. However, 2021 was the year with the most significant variability in yields, with plots with high and low yields (Figure 7b). The yield data of the studied plots show a slightly higher yield in VA compared to VB.

Figure 7. Distribution of Yield in different years (2017-2022) in different farms in VB (Left) and VA (Right).

To determine which plots may have been affected by heat waves, it is necessary to establish plots with specific characteristics and compare them to the same plots from different years. Once this is done, it will be possible to evaluate the stage of plant development in each plot for years with and without heat wave effects. This will assist in understanding the impact of heat waves on crop yields and distinguish them from other management factors.

The phenological stage at which the crop is found is essential in terms of the heat wave's effect on production. Of the selected plots, two were chosen where there was a 40-50 % reduction in yield in 2020 compared to 2019, and another where there was no reduction in production compared to the previous year. However, identifying the phenological moment of each of the plots involves keeping a record that is not usual. A study of the development of vegetation cover was used to identify the phenological moment of the crop. Furthermore, as a historical study was to be carried out, it was necessary to use information from the plot with historical data. For this reason, the normalized vegetation index (NDVI) obtained from satellite images was selected as a good tool to characterise the development of the crop (Campillo et al, 2019). Figure 8 shows the evolution of NDVI (from Sentinel 2) for the two years (2019 and 2020) in the three selected plots: two plots (Figure 8a and 8b) with yield declines recorded and another plot (Figure 8c) without yield declines. The crop's flowering periods have been identified in each of the plots, considering these periods from the moment when the maximum NDVI was reached, ten days before and after this point.

The data obtained from the analysis of the critical moment coincided with the period of abnormally high maximum and minimum temperatures, which occurred in 2020 during the period from 6 to 31 July. This period was identified as a critical period for the crop, coinciding with flowering and fruit set stages. The data indicated that plots, where the crop was in the crucial period, experienced decreased production. In contrast, crops outside this period did not register a significant decline.

Figure 8. NDVI dynamics in three different farms for 2019 and 2020: (a) and (b) farms with damage and (c) farms without damage.

CONCLUSIONS

- Over the last five years, the number of days of heat stress due to heat waves has increased in the processing tomato crop.
- In Extremadura, the temperature increase negatively affected yields in the tomato-growing areas of Guadiana's Vegas Bajas and Vegas Altas.
- It is essential to conduct a study with more plots to analyze the effects of heat waves' effects during specific crop growth stages. This will help establishing protocols for implementing strategies to reduce the resulting damage.
- Studying various agronomic management techniques to mitigate such damage, which is the next step once the problems caused by heat waves and the most vulnerable phase of crops have been identified.
- By studying 5-day climate prediction models and using satellite imagery, we can broadly identify the areas likely to be affected by heat waves.
- Crop phenology is a differentiating factor during periods of high temperatures, with flowering and fruit set being critical. NDVI, as an indicator of crop development, can identify the critical time for damage assessment and applied mitigation strategies.

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